
HISTORY OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF STATISTICAL SERVICE IN TURKESTAN

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Introduction

The beginning of the formation of a statistical service in Turkestan is associated with the conquest of the Kokand Khanate by Russia, the military operations of the tsarist army and the creation at the headquarters of the Turkestan region in 1866 of a statistical committee “for collecting purely military information and general statistics”¹.

With the formation in 1867 of a new administrative unit - the Turkestan Governor-General for the collection and processing Turkestan began to deal with statistical information statistical committee created (January 22, 1868) by order of K. P. Kaufman. A.K. Heine was appointed chairman of this committee, and N.A. Mayev was appointed secretary. After A.K. Heine left his service in Turkestan in 1869, the chairmen of the committee were the Syrdarya military governors.

The Turkestan Statistical Committee was supposed to collect, check and put into systematic order all the information necessary for the military department; provide these materials for the performance of military statistical work; carry out other types of statistical work as decided by the General Staff. He was also responsible for organizing statistical surveys, developing and publishing their materials.

There was a break of 2.5 years in the meetings of the Turkestan Statistical Committee, from February 1868 to August 20, 1870. After the resumption of the committee's work, a decision was made to publish a collection of statistical materials. In 1872, the first issue of a valuable scientific and local history publication, "Materials for Statistics", was published.

Turkestan region" ¹.

The preface to the collection said: in Turkestan "everything is new, everything lives a unique life, in a unique environment, which we do not encounter in any of our other southern and eastern outskirts. While the scientists of the Tashkent society and individual researchers will little by little accumulate a mass of information and scientific data, exploring the diverse manifestations of the nature of Turkestan and its life, the local statistical committee will also gradually, step by step, collect and group statistical material, without which scientific research is incomplete and unclear and which serves them as a strong and reliable support ²."

The compilers of the collection expressed the hope that the yearbook "will truly be a necessary tool for everyone who wants to study Turkestan, in any respect." Thanks to the efforts of the workers of the Turkestan Statistical Committee, the yearbooks included a large number of diverse materials: articles, studies, essays and notes on archeology, history, ethnography, topography, geography, economics and statistics of the Turkestan region.

The first issue of "Materials" was devoted mainly to demographic statistics and its features in Turkestan. Subsequent issues had varied content and were typical collections of scientific and local history in nature, compiled with the participation of a team of authors. A total of 5 issues were published (1872 - 1876). The second issue of "Materials" was formed by combining into one book articles

¹ Materials for statistics of the Turkestan region // Yearbook, publication of the Turkestan Statistical Committee / Ed. N. A. Maeva. Vol. 1. - St. Petersburg, 1872. - 237 p.

²Materials ... vol. 1.-S. 3.

of local history content published in “Turkestan Gazette” for 1870 - 1871. Of great importance was the publication in issue III of “Materials” of one of the first bibliographic indexes in the region, prepared by N. V. Dmitrovsky.

At the same time, historical essays were given about Asian Tashkent (N. A. Maeva), about Semipalatinsk and the state of trade (I. Zemlyanitsyna), “Essays on the Gissar Range and the mountain bekts of the Bukhara Khanate” (N. A. Maeva), etc.

“Satisfying scientific goals, the committee attaches to the figures presented by them an independent importance and truthfulness, which will result from the absence of any administrative considerations that preceded the collection of statistical information - and at the same time, at least partially, will satisfy the curiosity of Russian society, which is attentive to the new acquisition of Russia and the curiosity of many scientific societies with their works on the study of this region...”³, said the document justifying the purpose and objectives of the statistical service in Turkestan.

The grassroots apparatus of the statistical service was represented by administrative officials of the police department: city mayors, district police officers, bailiffs, and volost foremen. Their responsibilities included the collection and initial processing of the received facts - primary statistical material on the characteristics of the monitored phenomena. Information about the natural movement of the population of the Orthodox faith was recorded by clergy and their reports were transmitted to the ecclesiastical department. A large amount of various information was collected through departments and by private orders: materials from the Ministry of Railways, the Ministry of Construction, the Ministry of Trade and Industry, the Ministry of Public Education, etc. At the same time, people who did not have special training often worked as registrars. Even the

³Dmitrovsky N. _ V. Bibliographic index of books and articles on Central Asia from the end of the last century to 1869 // Materials... Issue III - St. Petersburg, 1874.

most conscientious performers, not having sufficient knowledge of the necessary methodology, made many errors in observations and processing.

The Statistical Committee also played a significant role in raising the issue of establishing local (peripheral) committees in the region. At the beginning of 1872, the Committee raised “the issue of expanding statistical research in the Turkestan region by establishing local statistical committees in the regions and cities of the region” and developed a project for their organization ⁴.

From the first days of its activity, the Turkestan Statistical Committee petitioned the colonial administration for the creation of a public library, the establishment of the title of corresponding members, and permission to publish a newspaper under it, which, along with government orders, would publish “scientific works related to the study of the region ⁵.”

Among the first corresponding members of the Committee, elected on August 20 and September 2, 1870, were famous figures from the first scientific societies of the region - G. A. Aminov, S. I. Zhilinsky, A. V. Kaulbars, A. A. Kushakevich, N. F. Petrovsky. A.P. Fedchenko and others. Their works provided statistical information, which included not only data from regional and regional annual reports, local censuses, but also individual articles and materials from various authors. For example, in issues III - V of “Materials” we find such major works as “Military topographical sketch of the mountainous country of the upper reaches of the river. Zeravshan” by G. A. Aminov; “Statistical information on the mountain Tyumen of the Zeravshan district” for 1877.” G. Arendarenko and a number of others.

Already in 1870, a newspaper in the Uzbek language, “Turkestan Newspaper,” began to be published as a supplement to the “Turkestan Gazette,” and from 1887 to 1916, “Turkestan Native Newspaper.”

⁴ Project for organizing local statistical committees in the Turkestan region "Materials for statistics of the Turkestan region. Yearbook. - St. Petersburg, 1874. Issue III. - pp. 196-199.

⁵Lunin B.V. From the history of the activities of statistical committees of the Turkestan region/Social sciences in Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 1962. - No. 6. - P. 33.

The unofficial parts of these newspapers served as a source of a wide variety of information on the nature, economics, history, archeology, and ethnography of the region. V. V. Bartold, V. L. Vyatkin, I. Yu. Krachkovsky, N. I. Veselovsky, V. F. Oshanin, A. P. Fedchenko, A. A. Divaev and many others presented their publications here. The activities of the Turkestan Statistical Committee are also associated with preparatory measures for the creation of a Public Museum in Tashkent, opened in 1876.

Obtaining correct statistical information required lengthy and painstaking work. So, for example, information about the receipt of taxes, arrears, etc. was documented on time and in the correct form by the volost boards, but most of the other information was written by them at random, approximately, or, as they themselves admitted, "out of the blue" or "from the wall." Therefore, if the volost government increased or decreased, for example, the number of seeds sown, then it did this not on the basis of any statistical observations, but guided only by general considerations about the harvest of a given year, in comparison with the previous one. Therefore, the statistician, using this information, could not draw any definite conclusions about the quantitative composition of certain phenomena.

conclusion

From the above it is not difficult to see that the Turkestan statistical committees were far from meeting their purpose. The question of transforming the statistical part in Turkestan and in the Russian Empire as a whole has arisen more than once. A corresponding bill was introduced into the State Duma, which had a lot of shortcomings. Its main drawback was that it did not provide for any proper systematic organization of local institutions that collected and delivered information. At the same time, new responsibilities were established for them without a corresponding increase in their funds. This did not change anything in the essence of the provision of the statistical part, and although the State Duma adopted the bill, the State Council rejected it.

It is appropriate here to provide some data on the costs of maintaining statistical committees in different countries. In Russia, the annual expenditure was 80 thousand rubles throughout the empire, of which 55 thousand were spent on maintaining personal personnel. The total amount of this expense is negligible, if you keep in mind that in the United States they spent up to 2.5 million on this. rubles, in Germany up to 2 million rubles per year only for government statistical institutions. Little Switzerland spent a little more than 1000 rubles, and the small state of Denmark spent a little less than Russia - 60 thousand rubles ¹.

It should also be noted that during the existence of regional statistical committees in Turkestan, they published many works, among which there are some that deserve serious attention. The information they collected about population and crops was not without significance, especially when it was necessary to compare these data throughout Russia.

By the beginning of the 20th century, the tasks of government statistics on a local scale were reduced mainly to obtaining digital data on the so-called “people's welfare” of Turkestan. These data were collected by regional statistical committees and were limited to the development and compilation of current statistical reports, which, as a rule, served as an appendix to the reports of regional governors. A special place among the publications of the committees was occupied by regional reviews with detailed information about the political and administrative structure of the regions, taxes and taxes, the national economy, irrigation systems, communications, healthcare, education, etc. In the reviews, along with statistical materials, articles of individual authors.

In total, the statistical committees published up to 100 issues of reviews, including: “Reviews of the Fergana region for 1884 - 1913.” ⁶, “Reviews of the Syrdarya region for 1886 - 1913.”, “Reviews of the Samarkand region for 1888 - 1910.”, “Reviews of the Semirechensk region for 1892 - 1912.” ⁷ and “Reviews of

¹Reviews of the Fergana region for 1884-1913//New Margilan-Skobelev, 1889-1916.

⁷Reviews of the Semirechensk region for 1892 - 1912. - Faithful, 1893 - 1914.

the Transcaspian region for 1891 -1914.”⁸. The review materials represent a valuable source for studying the socio-economic life of Turkestan during the colonial period.

Translations of eastern manuscripts were also published on the pages of the works of statistical committees: V. L. Vyatkin - Samarkand and its environs in the past according to the description of Babur Mirza, translation from “Babur-name”. V. L. Vyatkin “Samarkand Vilayet (Translation from “Rissol of Muhammad Salih” (SKSO, 1897); N. S. Lykoshin “Translation of “Rissol-i-Tarikat” (SMSSDO, VII, 1899); “The Wisdom of Hazrat-Sultan- Arifin-Khoja-Ahmad-Yassavi”. Translated from Turkic by N. S. Lykoshin (SMSSDODH, 1901), etc.

At the same time, many reference materials were published about government institutions of Turkestan and their activities. The increasing complexity of the administrative functions of the colonial administration required more complete and reliable information about various aspects of life in Turkestan in order to develop economic and social policy measures. Because of this, there was an active process of development of current statistics, and the practice of accounting expanded in all spheres of society.

So, the formation of a permanent statistical service, the development of various forms of statistical research in the region, allows us to talk about statistical practice as a special direction in the activities of the colonial state apparatus.

Turkestan authors, through their works, made a certain contribution to the development of statistics subordinate to the Central Statistical Committee and individual departments. A characteristic feature of their research was the substantiation of the thesis that already in the early period of its formation the statistical service developed in an independent direction. Strongly opposing the limitation of statistical tasks, the researchers chose to describe the natural conditions, territory, climate, population, economy, traditions, health care,

⁸Reviews of the Transcaspian region for 1891 - 1914. - Ashgabad. 1893 - 1914.

education and other objects characterizing the state of Turkestan in the second half of the 19th - early 20th centuries.

List of used literature

1. Turkestan commercial address-calendar for 1898.” - Samarkand, 1898.
2. .New Margilan-Skobelev, 1889-1916.
3. Reviews of the Transcaspian region for 1891 - 1914. - Askhabad. 1893 - 1914.
4. Bibliographic index of literature. - Tashkent, 1960. - P. 65 - 69.
5. Yearbook, publication of the Turkestan Statistical Committee / Ed. N. A. Maeva. Vol. 1 .